

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF WATERCOLOR IN THE FORMATION OF PAINTING

Yunusaliev M.T.

Senior Lecturer of the Department of Fine Arts, Faculty of Arts, Fergana State University.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7855500>

Abstract. *In this article, students-teachers-artists will learn that watercolor painting is not accidental in science, these are masterpieces of practical art, created in different ways, which were used in the folk spirit in all countries in the process of development from the time of the primitive communal system of mankind to ours. days, as well as each to provide analytical information about the creative potential of miracle-working artists of that time and the historical foundations of watercolor painting.*

Keywords: *rock inscriptions, technique, panel, watercolor, bright, transparent, nuance, plastic solution, papyrus, porcelain, silk painting, techniques, hot batik, miniature art, Renaissance, book graphics, illustration, decor, monochrome washing, Movarounnar. , Khorasan, Beauburnoma, manuscript, engraving, sketch, frieze, tempera, pastel, color combination, texture, classical method, font, tone, stylistic decision, series of works, free style, attractive, pictorial expression, portrait, motif, unusual, artist, skill, battle, lithography, craftsmanship, impression, study, sketchbook, rich color spot, colors, expressive gamut, richness of texture, tonality of colors, beautiful, attractive, harmony of colors, composition, color saturation, technique of flow and painting, artistic ideal.*

Art appeared in the early stages of the development of mankind, and the desire of primitive man to depict the surrounding being, to depict all the phenomena that occur daily in the constant struggle for their existence, has been observed since ancient times. Stone sculptures of idols, images on rocks, rock carvings, drawings on bones - all these are traces of a creative product created by a keen eye and skillful hands of a primitive artist. The value of art is incomparable in

man's understanding of the reality of life and his mastery of it, as well as in the sense of his place in front of him, and nature and events played an important role in its emergence. From the world of nature and the animal world, man learned to draw from nature the beautiful plastic solution of the human structure, and nature became the main factor in awakening in man a sense of art.

All types of art reflect different aspects of life and embody the uniqueness of the world and the beauty of man. However, the art of painting occupies a special and important place among them. The picture is able to fully express all the diversity of the world in which we live, its infinite diversity, and gives the key to understanding other types of art, feeling their emotional power.

Watercolor has always attracted many artists with its purity, transparency and brightness of colors, and watercolor painting occupies a large place in the work of painters. In the technique of watercolor, even the most subtle nuances of color can be significantly changed to another color,

using the moisture of the paints, gently and freely moving the brush while maintaining the spatial environment in a short period of time. Over the centuries, the methods of using watercolors have developed and changed in many ways, new possibilities and new research methods of creation have opened up. Colorful images carved on papyrus by the ancient Egyptians are known in history.

Similarly, in China and Japan, the use of water-based paints has become widespread. They worked on dyes for silk with great perfection. Especially famous and well-known in the world are works of fine art made of silk. Later, beautiful

batik-style silk curtains became popular, which were mainly decorated with panels. This expressiveness, subtle elegance of work amazes even a modern person. Looking at the colorful decorations on Chinese porcelain of that time, we see that the paintings on them are made in an easy and convenient technique, characteristic of watercolor paint. By the 12th century, the technology of watercolors and its techniques were revived in the art of Persian miniature and spread to the countries of Asia. It is known that in the eastern countries of the Middle Ages there was a renaissance in the field of fine arts. In particular, in connection with book graphics, a type of fine art known as miniature, that is, miniature, has been widely developed. As a result, wonderful schools of painting appeared in Arab (Baghdad), Iranian (Tabriz), Isfahan, Shiraz, Turk, Movarounnahr, India, Azerbaijan, Herat,

Bukhara and Samarkand.

Miniature art was formed as an illustration for old manuscripts and book decorations. These

schools were headed by a number of talented artists, such as Mirak Nakkosh, Kamoliddin Behzod, Qasim Ali, Ustad Gung, Abdullah ibn Fazil, Ota Mirak, Kesu, Ustad Shamsiddin, Abdul Baki Tabrizi. The term "miniature" comes from the Latin - "minium" from the name of red paint *, ancient manuscripts and miniature art of different peoples have come down to us. In the XIV-XV centuries, thanks to the art of miniature, watercolor was widely spread in the Movarunnahr and Khorasan regions of Central Asia and was used by masters of their time in wonderful schools of painting, such as Samarkand, Herat, Bukhara, Tabriz, Shiraz, , Isfahan. Painting technology has improved in a unique way. This includes the artists of the Tabriz school of figurative painting Pir Syed Ahmad, Maulana Khalil Mirza, Shahrukhi,

Mirak Nakkosh, Khoja Muhammad Nakkosh, the famous artist of the Herat school of figurative

painting and many others, such as the great artist of his time Kamoliddin Behzad. Actors can be cited as an example. The unique miniatures and decorative manuscripts created by Kamoliddin Behzad and his students played an important role in the development of the Herat school. They contributed not only to the treasure of world art, but also to the formation of watercolor art in the East with their priceless creative works created in watercolor. In the 16th century in India, a unique book of Indian painting "Boburnoma" was created, which includes the best miniature masterpieces of Samarkand, Herat, Bukhara, Tabriz, Shiraz and local Indian schools. This work contains the memoirs of the famous statesman, commander, poet, thinker and philanthropist Zahiridin Muhammad Babur. Ninety-six miniatures of the Beauburnom manuscript are the work of over forty talented artists. The samples of artistic creativity, created by them with a sense of beauty, rich in sophistication, elevated "Beauburnom" to the rank of an eternal masterpiece of art.

By the XVII-XVIII centuries in Europe, watercolor became an additional complementary part of many types of art: engravings, drawings and frescoes, as well as various graphic materials such as gouache, tempera, pastel widely used in mixed media. Among the well-known artists of that time, it was difficult to find an artist who did not turn to watercolors. In the Renaissance, the technical possibilities of watercolors were first discovered by A. Dürer. He achieved technical excellence by mixing honey products with paints and performing amazing creative work on them. A. Durer was only 17-18 years old when he was engaged in such scientific and creative work. Watercolor art becomes a serious independent art only in the 18th century, first in England, and then in France, Italy and other countries.

England is rightfully considered the classic country of watercolor painting. England's unique insular nature, with its unique climate and fog, and the constant changes in atmospheric phenomena, played a major role in the development of the watercolor technique, as if they suggested the use of watercolor as a transparent paint. In the 17th century, English watercolor became more and more picturesque, moving from transparent monochrome strokes to the technique of multicolor painting. John Cosens, W. Turner,

Constable, Richard Bonington and Thomas Gertin were the leaders of the English watercolor schools. They are from a layer of air in watercolor they created a painting with a vivid and spatial

look, depicting shimmering sunlight in perspective, and discovered the exemplary classical method in watercolor. Until now, landscapes created in watercolor by English artists have their own national characteristics and occupy a leading place among the genres of fine art. With their examples, English artists practically proved to artists of other European countries that the possibilities of watercolor technique are endless in a richer depiction of the

diversity of nature. As a result, well-known watercolor artists such as Alma Tadema, Lawrence,

Cooper, Varro, Whistler, and others developed in Europe. In the 19th century, English watercolor painting had a significant influence on French artists such as Jericho and Delacroix, and gave them a strong impetus to the development of their creativity. Jericho, who visited England in the last years of his life, created a real multi-color series of works, distinguished by a unique stylistic solution for painting in a tone suitable for the watercolor genre. Delacroix and a number of other

artists promoted a new creative approach in all types of graphics, effectively using the watercolor technique. They have taken their unique watercolor technique to a high level in creating paintings and graphic sketches created in a light and free style with eye-catching visual expression. As a result, thanks to these popular new approaches to creativity, watercolor art in France was freed from the old traditional influence of the English school. French artists such as Édouard Detail, the painter Gustave

Doré, the graphic artist Honoré Domi, the lithographer and portrait miniature painter Isobe, all successfully created in their own way in watercolor.

The influence of the English school penetrates into Germany through French artists. Eduard Hildebrandt, Caspar Friedrich, Franz Kruger can be cited as examples of famous German masters of watercolor. The fact that Eduard Hildebrandt is a skilled watercolorist is reflected in many of his works. The artist, who had the ability to immediately detect supernatural phenomena in nature, loved to "dazzle the imagination of the audience" with magical colors.

In the 19th century, watercolor was perfected in Italy. Italian artists have reached a level of perfection in their work in terms of precision, richness of motifs and ease of technique, and have far advanced from English art. We can cite an example of the Italian landscape painters Djigan, as well as Corridi and others, who express the nature of Italy in a bright and attractive way.

In Russia, watercolor paints began to develop from the 18th century, in particular, the landscape genre developed under the influence of the art of general realism and enriched its technique. The achievements of watercolor made it possible not only to create a painting, but also to distinguish it as an independent art form, in which the whole community of all prominent painters showed themselves. Landscapes, portraits and other creative works created in watercolor are valued equally with works created in other types of art. The bright development of the painting of the Russian watercolor school as an independent type dates back to the 19th century. P. F. Sokolov, K. P. in watercolor. Bryullov, S. Shchedrin, A.A. Many Russian artists, such as Ivanov, I. N. Kramskoy, I. E. Repin, A. V. Fonvizin, V. Surikov, V. Serov, A. P. Ostroumov-Lebedeva, left their wonderful creative examples.

It is impossible to imagine Russian watercolor painting without V. I. Surikov. V. I. Surikov is a great artist who left an indelible mark on the history of fine arts with his canvases created in the historical genre. In 1873, he began to study with the teacher of the artist-teacher P. Chistyakov and learned from him the secrets of art. P. Chistyakov played a big role in the development of the artist's creative personality. The ability to look for new techniques and try them in practice was gradually formed under the influence of his teacher. Almost on all trips, Surikov always drew sketches in watercolor, because the watercolor technique allows you to quickly convey impressions will allow. Therefore, Surikov, like, perhaps, all Russian artists, used oil paint and watercolor in the creative process, without separating them from each other. He is preparing for large canvases; he used watercolors to create sketches and perform studies for them. In the creative

process, the watercolor technique was Surikov's constant companion for its speed and convenience. In the 1880s he flourished in watercolor art. During this period, Russian watercolor art was completely free from all foreign influences. V. I. Surikov found his creative path as a result of a deep study of the techniques of great artists and became a master of watercolor painting. Based on the essence of the content of each work, he was looking for an artistic solution, using the rich possibilities of watercolor technique. Some of his works are made in the air by the method of light scattering, while others create an expressive range of colors with rich color spots.

I.E. Repin, the great artist of the Russian people, famous for his creative works in the genre of portraits in the history of fine arts, with his extraordinary technical skills, was able to enter the spiritual world of a person and skillfully depicted it, enriching the watercolor art even more. He created watercolor portraits and sketches for paintings on large canvases. I. Repin was a thoughtful psychologist who created deep thoughtful images imbued with humanitarian feelings in all his works. At this time, another Russian artist M. Vrubel showed his amazing skill in watercolor painting, who stood out for his unique creations in various genres of fine art. In the works he created, the unique aspects of using unexpected techniques were clearly visible. Perhaps because of this, his work has become one of the most amazing pages in the history of art. The harmony of colors and the richness of texture, the tonality of colors is more beautiful and attractive, and the graphic images, which skillfully performed the live perception of the image, are preserved in watercolor sheets. His watercolors sparkled with brilliant facets, like a precious magic stone. Poetic beauty can also be seen in the landscapes of M. Vrubel. The concept of color in watercolor art was of great importance to him. The gamut of colors, the perfect expression of its unity, this ability of his creative imagination and the great gift of colors prompted him to work. One of the outstanding artists and theorists I. Grabar rightly considered M. Vrubel the best watercolorist in the history of Russian art.

A. Ostroumova-Lebedeva is a master of pure watercolor, an artist who has worked in this technique all her life. He skillfully used the surface of the paper as white, skillfully mastering the

characteristics of watercolor paints. The artist did not paint excessively and unevenly, on the contrary, he carefully kept the surface of the paper clean and tidy. Because it was difficult to express the spatial position of air in a light environment on a rough surface. A. Ostroumova-Lebedeva diligently studied watercolor materials and tools throughout her life and tried to improve them. As a result of his extensive creative research to develop the watercolor technique, his technique was written about with excitement and love.

The achievements of the famous masters of watercolors of the past did not leave Uzbek painters indifferent and became the basis for the development of such painting in Uzbekistan. By the 60s of the last century, the art of watercolor occupied one of the important places in the creative life of artists of our republic. Many Uzbek artists who enjoyed the unique beauty of our Motherland; Yu. Tansikboev, K. Cheprakov, I. Yurovsky, G. Shevyakov, V. Akudin, G.I. Chiganov, Yu.I. Taldykin created many paintings in watercolor. In their paintings, nature is full of beauty, and they managed to miraculously revive nature, expressing in an unexpected way with light brush strokes a pleasant image of their beloved land. They, representatives of the older generation, passed on their experience and skill, their sincere and respectful devotion to the art of youth on the way to a higher and nobler goal than themselves. Young artists who understood this well continued, developed and enriched watercolor art with their creations. In recent years, bright aspects of the creativity of talented artists have appeared in Uzbek watercolors. R. Choriev, M. Sodikov, G. Boymatov, V. Apukhtin

showed excellent technical skills in watercolor painting. Bright and technically colorful paintings by Marat Sodikov have a unique creative character, and he created wonderful compositions in the technique of easily flowing paints on the surface of wet paper, in various ways and gradually softening it. The ability of the artist to accurately, easily and freely apply strokes, increase or decrease color saturation (brightness), skillfully use the technical capabilities of applying color spots with a wet stream testifies to the high skill of the artist. The literal meaning of such a study is that the artist creates an artistic ideal in the content of his work.

Creative groups of watercolor masters were organized by the Union of Artists of the Republic, and a program of

extensive tours around the country played an important role in the development of watercolor painting in Uzbekistan. These creative teams are of international importance, and the best watercolor artists from the Baltic countries, Russia and the CIS participated in them. Their creative journey through the colorful and beautiful landscapes of Uzbekistan was very interesting. Starting from the slopes of the mountains, unique historical cities, rich in historical monuments, Khiva and Bukhara and Samarkand, which have no equal in color, were embodied in watercolor in the spirit of a fairy tale. In the course of their creative journey, they got acquainted with the work of folk craftsmen and enriched the exhibition materials with their vivid impressions. Their work was distinguished by its watercolor style and artistic skill.

The world is beautiful and interesting. The task of all art forms is to express the beauty, complexity and versatility of this amazing discovery of the universe in colorful or simple handwriting. Today, watercolor artists successfully solve this problem with their stylistic skill.

REFERENCES

1. Khalilov R.Sh. Study guide "WATERCOLORS" Tashkent 2009 (Pages 6-15)
2. Pugachenkova G. Galerkina O. "MINIATURES OF CENTRAL ASIA" Moscow. "Fine Arts" 1979. (- 208 p.)
3. Rahim Hasanov. "FINE ARTS BASIC" Gafur Ghulam Publishing Association. TASHKENT – 2009. (Pages 47-67)
4. Khudoyberganov R.A. "Fundamentals of Color Science". study guide - T., 2006. (Page 180)
5. Yunusaliev M. "RANGTASVIR" Watercolor technique. Ferghana 2022. (Pages 7-11)
6. Курбанова, Б. М., Юнусалиев, М., & Арзиева, Н. (2022). ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТЕХНИКИ: АКВАРЕЛЬ, МАСЛО И ГУАШЬ. *Research Focus*, 1(2), 319-325.
7. Kurbanova, B., Khurshid, M., & Tokhirjon, S. (2022, May). THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF A SYSTEMATIC APPROACH TO TEACHING IN THE FINE ARTS. In *Archive of Conferences* (pp. 105-107).
8. Курбанова, Б. М., Юнусалиев, М., & Арзиева, Н. (2022). ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТЕХНИКИ: АКВАРЕЛЬ, МАСЛО И ГУАШЬ. *Research Focus*, 1(2), 319-325.
9. Sulaymanova, S. (2023). IMPORTANCE OF THE PATCHWORK NEEDLEWORK IN STUDY WHICH HAS GIVEN A BIRTH TO APPLIED ARTS, BASED MUCH ON ANCIENT OLD-TIME TRADITION. *Science and innovation*, 2(C4), 9-12.
10. Yunusaliev, M. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE SCALE OF THE VIEWING ANGLE IN PERSPECTIVE. *Science and innovation*, 2(A4), 15-20.
11. Sulaymanova, S. (2023). IMPORTANCE OF THE PATCHWORK NEEDLEWORK IN STUDY WHICH HAS GIVEN A BIRTH TO APPLIED ARTS, BASED MUCH ON ANCIENT OLD-TIME TRADITION. *Science and innovation*, 2(C4), 9-12.
12. Юнусалиев, М., Мадаминов, Н., & Мамуров, А. (2022). МЕТОДИКА РАБОТЫ НАД РИСОВАНИЕМ НАТЮРМОРТА. *Research Focus*, 1(2), 326-332.
13. Kakharovna, A. M., Tadjimatovich, Y. M., Rakhmatovich, S. O., & Mirzahamdammovna, Q. B. (2021). Modern Approaches to the Teaching of Fine Arts. *Solid State Technology*, 64(2), 4250-4254.
14. Barchinoy, K., Sevarakhon, S., & Mukhammadkodir, Y. (2021). Effective methods of teaching fine arts and drawing at school.
15. Nodirjon, M., Abdusalom, M., & Ozodbek, S. (2021). Technologies of teaching fine arts with modern methods.
16. Yunusaliyev, M. T., & Sulaymonova, S. B. (2022). QALAMTASVIRDA PERSPEKTIVANING AHAMIYATI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(12), 1039-1044.
17. Юнусалиев, М., Мадаминов, Н., & Мамуров, А. (2022). МЕТОДИКА РАБОТЫ НАД РИСОВАНИЕМ НАТЮРМОРТА. *Research Focus*, 1(2), 326-332.
18. Yunusaliyev, M. T. (2022). RANGTASVIRDA KONTRAST VA NYUANS'LARNING AHAMIYATI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(10-2), 174-182.

19. Sadikovna, S. G., Kurbonova, B., Akhmedova, N., & Sulaymanova, S. (2020). FUNDAMENTALS OF PROFESSIONALISM DEVELOPMENT ON THE EXAMPLE OF PRACTICAL EXERCISES ON FORMING THE SKILLS AND SKILLS OF FUTURE TEACHERS. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(6), 8894-8903.
20. Mirzahamdorova, K. B., Erkinovna, A. N., & Jumadillaevich, S. R. (2021). Use of Innovative Educational Technologies in Fine ARTS Classes of Higher Education Institutions. *European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements*, 2(4), 25-27.
21. Sulaymanova, S. B. Q. (2022). BADIY YO 'NALISHDAGI OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA TASVIRIY SAN'ATDA PERSPEKTIVAGA RIOYA QILISH METODIKASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK NAZARIYA VA TA'LIM AMALIYOTIDAGI TAHLILI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(10-2), 16-23.
22. Sulaymanova, S. B. Q. (2022). BADIY OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA TASVIRIY SAN'AT FANINI O'QITISHGA BO'LGAN EHTIYOJNING OSHISHI VA UNING BUGUNGI HOLATI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(10-2), 89-96.
23. TA'LIM, B. Y. N. O., & TASVIRIY, M. (2022). SAN'ATDA PERSPEKTIVAGA RIOYA QILISH METODIKASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK NAZARIYA VA TA'LIM AMALIYOTIDAGI TAHLILI Sulaymanova Sevaraxon Bahodirjon qizi.
24. Barchinoy, K., Sevaraxon, S., & Mukhammadkodir, Y. (2021). Effective methods of teaching fine arts and drawing at school.
25. Сулайманова, С., Омонов, Д., & Аъзамжонов, А. (2022). Алишер Навоий асарларидан бадий олий таълим муассасаларида тасвирий санъатни ўқитиш жараёнида фойдаланишнинг зарурияти. *Research Focus*, 1(2), 272-277.
26. Sulaymonova, S. B. Q. (2021). TASVIRIY SAN'AT ORQALI DUNYO SIVILIZATSIYASINI O'RGANISH OMILLARI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(6), 730-735.
27. Ozodbek, S., Muhammadjon, O. R., & Sevaraxon, S. (2022). MARKAZIY OSIYO XALQLARI TASVIRIY SAN'AT TARIXINING FANDAGI O'RNI. *Research Focus*, 1(2), 259-263.
28. Sulaymanova, S. (2022). PEDAGOGICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR IMPROVING THE METHOD OF OBSERVING PERSPECTIVES WHEN STUDENTS INDEPENDENTLY COMPLETE TASKS IN THE AREAS OF PAINTING AND PENCIL DRAWING. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 1559-1564.
29. Yunusaliyev, M. T., & Sulaymonova, S. B. (2022). AKVAREL TEXNIKASIDA YORUG'LIK VA RANG MUNOSABATLARIDA RANGLAR GAMMASINING AHAMIYATI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(12), 850-857.
30. Sulaymanova, S. (2022). TALABALAR RANGTASVIR VA QALAMTASVIR FALARIDAN TOPSHIRIQLARNI MUSTAQIL BAJARISHDA PERSPEKTIVAGA RIOYA QILISH METODIKASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA PEDAGOGIK TALABLAR. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 1559-1564.